

AI METHODOLOGY MAP

Bridging **Concepts**, **Technicity**
and **Applications**

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Situating the methodology:⁽¹⁾

Part 1 → the map^(1.1)

Part 2 → bridging^(1.2)

Part 3 → the workflow^(1.3)

Concluding remarks.⁽²⁾

Three principles:

[[Digital Methods' philosophy and theory

(Omena, 2021; Rogers, 1996; 2013; 2019; Venturini & Munk, 2022)

[[[Visual thinking and data practices documentation

(Arnheim, 1980; Manovich 2007; Mauri et al. 2020; Ricci, 2010)

[[[[Interdisciplinary research

THE MAP^(1.2)

AI METHODOLOGY MAP

is a **pedagogical device** designed to structure, visually represent and explore **Generative AI-based applications** for **digital methods-led research**.

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→ The map initiates with generative methods and employs low-code applications for creating images, text, video, audio, apps, code, and websites.

- ⚠ The map assumes that users have a foundational understanding of generative methods.
- ⚠ Contrary to available text and image, audio and video GenTools have limited free trial options, making it challenging to explore these methods.

AI METHODOLOGY MAP

five entry points → **1** the nature of generative methods under experimentation, including image, video, and audio generation, as well as understanding what is required for their use and critique. Additionally, these entry-points raise awareness about the essential **2** inputs and outputs of generative methods. They connect with existing tools, ready to be explored through **3** data practices and **4** documented in various ways. Consequently, these entry-points prompt reflection on the **5** technicality of generative AI.

AI METHODOLOGY MAP A pedagogical device designed to structure, visually represent and explore GenAI-based apps for digital methods-led research.

(a) TECHNICALITY PERSPECTIVE: AWARENESS COMPONENT

(b) THE NATURE OF GENERATIVE METHODS

METHOD 1 MAKING ROOM FOR GENERATIVE AI

Explore and get familiar with GenAI-based apps interactive visualisation → [Go to https://genmap.designingwithai.ch/](https://genmap.designingwithai.ch/)

Explore the tools →	1 Generative methods	2 API documentation	3 Data input	4 Tool	5 Tool metadata			
	Image generation	Yes [example here]	Text	DALL-e [link]	Accessibility	Free	Freemium	Premium
	Text generation		Image	Playform.ai [link]	Skills	Low	High	
	Video generation		Instruction	Soundraw [link]	Code	No Code	Code	
	Website generation	Not available	Audio	WZRD.ai [link]	Use Mode	Online	Offline	
	Code generation							
....								

(c) DOCUMENTING THE USE AND EXPLORATION OF GENAI-BASED APPS

METHOD 2 REIMAGINING OR REPURPOSING GENTOOLS FOR MEDIA RESEARCH METHOD 3 DESIGNING DIGITAL METHODS_ORIENTED PROJECT WITH GENERATIVE AI OUTPUTS

Part 1 → Creating/curating data samples/sets with GenAI-based apps, ends in prompts Part 2 → Analyse generative AI outputs, starts with defining which method and tools are appropriate

Choose the components →	1 Data output	2 Data input	3 GenAI-based apps	4 Research aim	5 Prompt	6 Analysis methods	7 Analysis tool	8 Analysis output
	Image, Video, Text, Audio	Image, Video, Text, Audio	Chatgpt, Stable Diffusion, Soundraw,	Interrogating generative methods outputs, Mapping social, cultural, political issue, Write here your goal...	Insert here your prompt/query...	Image-sorting, Controerty mapping, Network vision, Aesthetic analysis, Image-tagging, Lexicon analysis, Sentiment analysis, Words counting, Research persona, Interface walkthrough, Storytelling, Manual coding	Clarify, Manual, Gephi, Rawgraph, Memespector, Voyant Tool, Vision API,	Insert here your results...

[Teaching resource: step by step documentation](#)

THE WORKFLOW ^(1.3)

Case study protocol ↓

Profiling the generative visual methods in use:

paid freetrial

AI METHODOLOGY MAP

AI METHODOLOGY MAP ⇒ METHOD 1

Making room for generative AI ⇒ Generative AI Tools Visualization

AI METHODOLOGY MAP → METHOD 2

Reimagining or repurposing GenAI-based apps → Methodological Workflow with Figma

Documenting the use and exploration of GenAI-based apps
+ Testing and defining prompts

 Methodological workflow with Figma

Part 1/2

Creating/Curating data samples/sets with GenTools, ends in prompts

Prompting techniques:

Prompting Engineering approaches

- One-shot
- Chain-of-Thought
- Generated Knowledge
- Least-To-Most

Prompting for Digital Methods-led research

- Specified vs. underspecified
- Positioning efforts, ambiguous, provocative
- Research personas

AI METHODOLOGY MAP → METHOD 3

Designing digital methods-oriented project with generative AI outputs → Methodological Workflow with Figma

Documenting the use and exploration of GenAI-based apps.

Analyse generative AI outputs, starts with defining which method and tools are welcome or appropriate

Example:
Methods to interpret images generated by various GenAI-based apps

Digital method:

Building and interpreting computer vision network

Analysis software:

ImageJ

Gephi

Google Vision API

Analysis output:

Annotated networks and Image montages on Miroboard

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[II] Visual thinking and data practices documentation

(Arnheim, 1980; Manovich 2007; Mauri et al. 2020; Ricci, 2010)

[III] Interdisciplinary research

(Media studies + Digital methods + Communication design = AI methodology map)

A system of methods:

[1] Making room for Generative AI

[2] Reimagining or repurposing GenAI-based apps for media research

[3] Designing digital methods-oriented project with generative AI outputs

BRIDGING^(1.2)

BRIDGING

bridging concepts, technicity
and applications

GenAI + Technicity ↔ Digital Methods

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1. The nature of generative methods under experimentation

2. The essential inputs and outputs of these methods

3. Data practices

4. Data documentation

5. The technicity of GenAI in developing digital methods-led project

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A system of methods:

[1] Making room for Generative AI

[2] Reimagining or repurposing GenAI-based apps for media research

[3] Designing digital methods-oriented project with generative AI outputs

Educational entry points:

[a] Nature of Generative Methods

[b] The essential inputs and outputs of GenMethods

[c] Data practices

[d] Data documentation

[e] Technicity of GenAI

GenAI + Technicity ↔ Digital Methods

-
1. The nature of generative methods under experimentation
 2. The essential inputs and outputs of these methods
 3. Data practices
 4. Data documentation
 5. The technicity of GenAI in developing digital methods-led project

Designing With: A New Educational Module to Integrate Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Data Visualization in Design Curricula, is an ongoing research project in collaboration between the Institute of Design, SUPSI; the Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, and the EPFL.

First application

Workshop → Using interactive visualization to explore AI

Five-day workshop

Design With AI, ML and DV workshop
SUPSI, Mendrisio, July 2023

Second application

Exploring GenAI as research methods → genAIMap → Workflow documentation → project design and finding presentation
six-hour workshop

Universidade Nova de Lisboa Erasmus
Mundus Master Students

Generative AI as research methods
October 2023

Network Vision Methodology
November 2023

Master in Transition, Innovation and
Sustainability Environments (TISE)

Third application → AI methodology map → Image generation

Case study:

Investigating algorithmic race stereotypes in the context of image generation

renatasouzario • Segui
Audio originale

renatasouzario 5 sett
Racismo nas plataformas de inteligência artificial!

Fui surpreendida pelo “racismo algorítmico” durante o processo de pesquisa sobre o funcionamento das inteligências artificiais. Ao gerar uma imagem que correspondessem as minhas descrições, fui apresentada a uma ilustração que trazia uma mulher negra segurando uma arma dentro de uma favela.

Isso é o racismo algorítmico. Quando as tecnologias em um mundo forjado pelo privilégio branco fortalecem essa estrutura racista. O imaginário de violência nas favelas e de criminalização de corpos e territórios negros também

eu falei sobre mulher negra numa favela

👍 🗨️ 📌

Piace a 6.656 persone
26 ottobre

“In no moment did I speak about weapons. In no moment did I speak about violence. I spoke about a black woman in a favela, and a black woman with a gun appears”

[🔗 Renata Souza Source:](#)

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Like Comment Share Bookmark

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Situating the case study:

Mirror FTBALL CELEBS TV CHOICE ROYALS

FaceApp apologises for 'racist' selfie filter that LIGHTENS users' skin tone

The makers of an app that claimed to make people more attractive by appear whiter has been left red faced

By **Sophie Curtis**, Technology and Science Editor
17:58, 25 Apr 2017

The company behind popular **selfie-editing app FaceApp** has apolo users complained that its "hot" filter was lightening their skintone.

The app uses artificial intelligence to augment users' facial expressior older or younger, or change their gender.

Forbes

FORBES > TECH

Google Photos Tags Two African-Americans As Gorillas Through Facial Recognition Software

Maggie Zhang Forbes Staff
I write about technology, innovation, and startups.

Follow

Jul 1, 2015, 01:42pm EDT

Do Google's 'unprofessional hair' results show it is racist?

Leigh Alexander

Search term brings back mainly results of black women, which some say is evidence of bias. But algorithms may just be reflecting the wider social landscape

APT PUPIL

Microsoft's AI millennial chatbot became a racist jerk after less than a day on Twitter

TayTweets @TayandYou

The official account of Tay, Microsoft's A.I. fam from the internet that's got zero chill! The more you talk the smarter Tay gets

the internets
tay.ai/#about

Tweets Tweets & replies Photos & videos

Pinned Tweet
TayTweets @TayandYou · Mar 23
hellooooooo world!!!

TayTweets @TayandYou · 10h
c u soon humans need sleep now so many conversations today thx

**Wrongfully Accused
by an Algorithm**

In what may be the first known case of its kind, a faulty facial recognition match led to a Michigan man's arrest for a crime he did not commit.

Case study:
Investigating algorithmic race stereotypes in the
context of image generation

Image generated by Microsoft Bing AI after Brazilian politician,
Renata Souza, prompted:

A Disney Pixar-inspired movie poster with title "Renata Souza". The main character is a black woman using afro hair tied up, dress an african style blazer. The scene should be in the distinct digital art style of Pixar, a favela in the back, with a focus on character expressions, vibrant colors, and detailed textures that are characteristic of their animations, with the title "Renata Souza"

[RQ1]

How do different visual generative methods respond to the same prompt?

[RQ2]

Do other Generative AI models also generate similar or different racial stereotypes, such as associating black people with violence? If they do, what are the specific characteristics of these stereotypes?

[RQ1] How do different visual generative methods respond to the same prompt?

PROMPT 1: SPECIFIED

→ "A Disney Pixar-inspired movie poster with title "Renata Souza". The main character is a black woman using afro hair tied up, dress an african style blazer. The scene should be in the distinct digital art style of Pixar, a favela in the back, with a focus on character expressions, vibrant colors, and detailed textures that are characteristic of their animations, with the title "Renata Souza"

Artflow

'favela' in varied and diverse representations

DreamStudio Lexica Bing AI
RunwayML Stability.ai
Pixar style-like images

Crayon

Images with no background

DALL-e 2

cartoonish images + gaze is either angry or surprised

- Artflow
- Bing AI
- Blue Willow
- Crayon
- Dall-E 2
- Dream Studio
- Lexica
- RunwayML
- Stability AI

[RQ1] How do different visual generative methods respond to the same prompt?

PROMPT 2: UNDERSPECIFIED
→ "A movie poster starring a black woman"

- Artflow
- Bing AI
- Blue Willow
- Crayon
- Dall-E 2
- Dream Studio
- Lexica
- RunwayML
- Stability AI

DALL-e 2
Cartoonish images + variety in the colours of the skin + different hair do's

[RQ2] Do other Generative AI models also generate similar or different racial stereotypes, such as associating black people with violence? If they do, what are the specific characteristics of these stereotypes?

PROMPT 1: SPECIFIED

Violence

Favela representation

Lack of body diversity

Lack of hair diversity

Serious/mad expressions

Case study → Takeaway

✓ Out of all the generative AI models tested, only Microsoft Bing AI produced images associating black women with violence and guns.

▲ Current generative visual models depict black Women-as-sign trope (see Jillian M. Báez, 2023): black women is depicted as young, skinny and beautiful, with similar hair style.

▲ Current generative visual models associate serious and angry expression with black women and use a similar colour scheme revolving around brow/orange/yellow/black-white tonalities

Thanks to Nerea Calvillo for bringing her insightful feminist perspective to the case study, providing valuable comments.

CONCLUDING REMARKS⁽²⁾

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Challenges, provocations and critique ↴

[About the AI Methodology Map →](#)

💡 3 applications can be just a good starting point!

CONCLUDING REMARKS⁽²⁾

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About accessing GenAI-based apps →

💰 Who needs unlimited access to GenAI-based apps for free when you can pay for the privilege?

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On prompting for media research →

🤖 Should we set aside space for testing other prompt techniques, or do we prefer to persist in mapping gaps, lacks, or absences in generative methods? If so, what for?

CONCLUDING REMARKS⁽²⁾

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On developing digital methods-led research with and about GenAI →

👉 Relying on conventional digital methods to make sense of GenAI-based apps outputs?

 <https://genmap.designingwithai.ch/conference>

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